

The influence of the vegetation cycle on the mitigation of air pollution by a deciduous roadside hedge

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ABSTRACT

Vegetation barriers along roads can mitigate the effects of air pollution from traffic. Here, we measure a range of air pollutants in front and behind a hedge during the dormancy, greenup and part of the maturity vegetation cycle along with auxiliary variables. This is the first time a long time-series measuring multiple pollutants on both sides of a hedge is presented. This time-series allows assessing the influence of the annual vegetation cycle, wind direction and high versus low concentrations of both gaseous and particulate matter pollutants across a hedge. A marked jump in concentrations of particles happens after the hedge is greening up; this jump was not seen for gases. For example, a concentration difference for CO and PM₁ of −8%, −1% for PM_{2.5} and −3% for NO₂ and +10% for PM₁₀ during dormancy and greenup was measured. At the beginning of the maturity phase, all three PM fractions experience a rapid increase in concentration difference, not seen for gases, to −52% for PM₁, −44% for PM_{2.5} and −35% for PM₁₀. The effect of wind direction is shown to be minor. These measurements are a first step towards an accurate assessment of city-scale air pollution mitigation potential of hedge-like vegetation.

Capsule

The vegetation cycle influences the air pollution mitigation by roadside hedges differently that is demonstrated by a marked jump in particle concentration reduction after the hedge is greening up.

1. Introduction

Despite significant emission reductions over the last decades, air pollution continues to be an important environmental health problem in Europe (Annesi-Maesano, 2017). It is well known, that the highest air pollution concentrations are found in cities, where the population exposure is also highest due to the high population density (Guerreiro, Ortiz, de Leeuw, Viana, & Colette, 2018). To reduce the exposure to air pollution, generally, legislative (European Court of Auditors, 2018) and technological approaches (e.g. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2015) can be adopted. An idea that has gained prominence in recent years is the use of green infrastructure (e.g. trees and hedges) for air pollution exposure reduction along busy roadsides in cities as recently reviewed by Abhijith et al. (2017). Apart from the influence on air quality, green infrastructure also contributes to a range of other benefits for urban citizens and urban flora and fauna such as human health and

well-being (Kim & Miller, 2019), urban thermal comfort (Hami, Abdi, Zarehaghi, & Bin Maulan, 2019), urban stormwater management (Dhakal & Chevalier, 2017; Shaneyfelt et al., 2017), CO₂ sequestration and noise abatement (Gratani & Varone, 2013) and urban biodiversity (Borysiak, Mizgajski, & Speak, 2017). In this way, green infrastructure can contribute to achieving the UN sustainable development goal 3 “good health and well-being” and 11 “sustainable cities and communities”.

The effect of green infrastructure on air pollution is complicated since it depends on the geometry of the street, the geometry and species of the vegetation as well as local effects such as meteorology and emission strength (Kumar, Druckman et al., 2019; Kumar, Abhijith, & Barwise, 2019). A range of studies have studied the effect of urban trees for cities such as London (Tallis, Taylor, Sinnett, & Freer-Smith, 2011), Leicester (Jeanjean, Hinchliffe, McMullan, Monks, & Leigh, 2015) and the entire United States (Nowak, Crane, & Stevens, 2006), yielding concentration reductions in the order of 1%–7%. Likewise, the effect of green walls has been studied in a few studies and air pollution abatement has been reported (Morakinyo, Lam, & Hao, 2016; Pugh, MacKenzie, Whyatt, & Hewitt, 2012; Tong, Baldauf, Isakov, Deshmukh, & Zhang, 2016).

Large vegetation geometries, as found along highways, has also

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been the subject of numerous studies (Hagler et al., 2012; Lin et al., 2016; Steffens, Wang, & Zhang, 2012), however comparatively little has been published on small vegetation geometries, in the following referred to as “hedges”, as commonly found in urban areas (although there is a lack of evidence as to the total area/length of urban hedges; Blanus, Garratt, Cathcart-James, Hunt, & Cameron, 2019). Here, we define a “hedge” as an elongated vegetation type (length to width ratio larger than 2) of low average height (less than 4 m, since it is difficult to maintain high hedges), low width compared to height and foliage from the ground to the top of the canopy. Gromke, Jamarkattel, and Ruck (2016) studied hedges in street canyons in a wind tunnel and showed area-averaged concentration reductions up to 61 % compared to street canyons without hedges depending on hedge height and hedge permeability with the largest improvement observed for perpendicular wind directions. Al-Dabbous and Kumar (2014) studied the particle number concentration in the front, middle and back of a hedge next to a busy road and found up to 37 % reduction during crosswinds. Abhijith and Kumar (2019) measured the concentration reduction across the same hedge as used in the present study and found 43 % reduction for black carbon, 30 % reduction for particle number concentration, 15 % reduction for PM₁₀, 14 % reduction for PM_{2.5}, and 25 % reduction for PM₁. Tiwary, Reff, and Colls (2008) measured the concentration of PM₁₀ in front and behind a rural hedge and found the average collection efficiency to be 34 %. All the previous air quality measurement campaigns have been based on relatively short time series due to the labour intensiveness of the measurement techniques. This means that for example diurnal variation, weekly variation, and the influence of the vegetation cycle have therefore not been analysed, and the influence of meteorology has only been analysed to a limited extent. To form a better view of the controlling variables for the air pollution reduction potential in hedges, the air pollution was measured for the first time on both sides of a hedge over a several months’ time period and the dependency of the concentration differences on auxiliary variables were explored.

2. Methodology

2.1. Site description

The sampling site for the present study was a hedge on the edge of Stoke Park, Guildford, UK (Lon. 51.243999, Lat. -0.571478). Supplementary Information (SI) Figure S1 shows an overview of the location, and Fig. 1 shows a cross-section of the set-up. As can be seen from SI Figure S1, the hedge and the road are approximately aligned North-South. This site was chosen since it constitutes a long unobstructed hedge next to a busy road, and thus constitutes an ideal location for evaluating the effect of the hedge itself. For that same reason, the location has been used in a previous study (Abhijith & Kumar, 2019). The hedge is shielding a children’s playground, which further adds to the relevance of the location. The hedge is of the species

Horn beam (*Fagus sylvatica*) and has a width of 1.2 m, a height of 2.2 m and a distance to the road of 2 m. As seen in SI Figure S1, the opposite side of the road is lined with trees and behind the trees is a row of two-story detached houses. The site can thus be characterised as a typical open-road environment (Abhijith et al., 2017). In Abhijith and Kumar (2019) the average hourly vehicle number (averaged from 0800 h to 1800 h; local time) was counted to 1200 vehicles per hour. The present monitoring campaign was performed from 12 February 2019 to 18 June 2019 to elucidate the change in air pollution reductions as a function of the phases of the vegetation cycle: dormancy, greenup and maturity. Only dormancy, greenup and part of the maturity phases have been measured in the present study as a part of our study design, and the present study should thus be seen as a first step towards a more general understanding of the role of the vegetation cycle in air pollution mitigation of deciduous vegetation. Future studies are recommended to measure the entire vegetation cycle during multiple seasons and for multiple vegetation species to explore the replicability of the present results.

2.2. Instrumentation

Two high-end low-cost air quality monitors were mounted in front and behind the hedge as illustrated in Fig. 1. The mounting height was 174 cm for the monitor in front of the hedge, and 150 cm for the monitor behind the hedge. These heights were chosen with the aim of representing adult breathing height but also taking into account practical constraints. Only a few previous studies have examined the vertical distribution of air pollutants in the lowermost two meters next to a road. The relative difference between the two heights is estimated to be 15 % for PM₁ and 7.5 % for PM_{2.5} based on the results from Kumar, Fennell, Langley, and Britter (2008), 1.3 % for PM₁₀ based on the results from Micallef and Colls (1998) and 16 % for NO₂ based on the results from Nakashima, Jones, Yamanobe, and Kajii (2014). It should be noted that previous studies on the vertical distribution of pollutants were conducted in street canyons (as opposed to open road conditions of the present study) without the presence of vegetation, and these number should therefore only be seen as estimates. Moreover, the focus of the present study is on the temporal variation of the concentrations to study the effect of the vegetation cycle, and the height difference is therefore expected to have a negligible influence on the results. The two monitors were mounted on the surface of the hedge to get the largest difference between the two sensors.

The low-cost air quality sensor is a custom-built system which measures carbon monoxide (CO) using an Alphasense CO-B4 sensor, Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) using an Alphasense NO2-B43F sensor, and PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ using a Plantower PMS5003 Dual System. The PM sensors have also been used in our previous work deploying smart citizen kits (Mahajan et al., 2020) and can log data internally on a SD card or on a digital platform (<https://smartcitizen.me/>). Air temperature and relative humidity were measured using a Sensirion SHT-31

Fig. 1. Cross-section of the road with the setup used for measuring the effect of the hedge on air pollution. Figure is approximately to scale (Clipart source: Pngtree.com).

sensor. The sensor closest to the road was running on mains power, and the sensor inside the park was running on battery. Both sensors record data at 1-minute temporal resolution. The PM sensor reports data as an integer, which creates uncertainty, especially on the low concentrations. The sensors are described in further details in [Camprodon et al. \(2019\)](#).

Auxiliary data on hourly averaged wind speed, wind direction and 12-hourly total precipitation were obtained from Farnborough Airport (lat. 51.276, lon. -0.776), which is about 14.72 km to the North-East of the monitoring site. Data were downloaded from the National Climatic Data Center, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (ncdc.noaa.gov). Download and averaging was then performed in one step using the `worldmet` package ([Carslaw, 2019](#)) in R.

2.3. Verification against high-end instruments

To verify the results from the low-cost sensors, two co-location campaigns were carried out in March 2019 and May 2019 over a period of 9 days. During these campaigns, a GRIMM aerosol monitor model 11-C was deployed on a stand close to the low-cost sensor outside the park. The co-location was carried out for a total of 45 h. For the co-location campaign in May 2019, a 2B NO₂/NO/NO_x monitor model 405 nm was also used as a reference instrument. The co-location covered the period from approximately 0900 h (local time) to approximately 1730 h to get a large variety of concentrations.

The verification was carried out by fitting a directly proportional relationship between the low-cost sensor and respectively the GRIMM aerosol monitor and the 2B NO₂/NO/NO_x monitor using robust linear regression for each pollutant separately since a visual inspection of the data showed that data were influenced by outliers. The fit was performed using the `lmrob` function from the `robustbase` package ([Maechler et al., 2019](#)) in R. The verification was carried out by computing the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the fit.

The data from the two co-location campaigns were merged for the PM measurements to one dataset used for verification since the relationship between the reference instrument and the low-cost sensor was shown to be approximately constant as quantified by Cohen's D ([Cohen, 1988](#)) between the residuals of the two datasets being in the order of 0.05 to 0.16.

2.4. Leaf area index measurements

Following the approach of [Abhijith and Kumar \(2019\)](#), the Leaf Area Index (LAI) of the hedge was measured with an Accu-PAR LP80 ceptometer. In this approach, the LAI is calculated from the change in Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) above and below the canopy of the vegetation. The above canopy PAR measurements were conducted as an average of 10 measurements, to prevent outliers influencing the result, taken away from any vegetation or other shadows. The measurements were taken with the ceptometer pointing in various directions along the 360 degrees circle to average over eventual shadows cast by the experimenter. The below vegetation PAR measurements were taken as an average of 10–15 measurements along the length of the hedge with approximately 1 m–1.5 m distance between the measurements. All LAI measurements were conducted at midday in sunny conditions or during cloudy conditions to prevent the influence of the solar zenith angle.

2.5. Statistical data analysis

Data have been quality controlled following the approach of [Ottosen and Kumar \(2019\)](#) with the exception that the minimum segment length for the mean value segmentation and the variance segmentation has been changed from 1000 to 1 data points, and the reference variance has been changed from the longest segment with a minimum segment length of 10,000 data points to the median of all segments with

a minimum segment length of 1000 data points. The results of this procedure are shown in SI Figures S2 and S3.

The time series curves have been presented in a smoothed format using a loess regression smoothing with a span width of 0.015 to allow easier visualisation. The span width corresponds to approximately 1.9 days. The loess regression was performed using the `loess` function in R. A comparison between the measurements and the smoothed time series can be found in SI Figures S4 and S5. Unless otherwise stated, all fits are made to the raw minute by minute data.

We divided the annual vegetation cycle, based on the LAI measurements, into four phases following the terminology of [Zhang et al. \(2003\)](#). The phases are (i) *greenup*, “the date of onset of photosynthetic activity” (defined by increasing LAI), (ii) *maturity*, “the date at which plant leaf green area is maximum” (defined by constant high LAI), (iii) *senescence*, “the date at which photosynthetic activity and green leaf area begin to rapidly decrease” (defined by decreasing LAI), and (iv) *dormancy*, “the date at which physiological activity becomes near zero” (defined by constant low LAI). The different phases of the vegetation cycle were determined by manual interpretation of the LAI time series curve.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Time series

[Fig. 2](#) shows the time series measurement for all five pollutants for the two air quality sensors. The time series have been smoothed to better show long-term variations. It is evident that the PM concentration is fluctuating between high and low concentrations as a result of weather, emissions and other parameters. For instance, the drop observed in the middle of February is caused by the half-term break (a public holiday in the UK), and the extended period of low concentrations at the beginning of March is caused by rain. That the rain has a large effect on time series of PM has been shown in several previous studies from China ([Guo et al., 2016](#); [Zheng, Xu, Li, Chen, & Li, 2019](#); [Luan, Guo, Zhang, & Guo, 2019](#)). The effect of holiday periods on roadside PM concentrations has likewise been shown previously (e.g. [Barmapadimos, Hueglin, Keller, Henne, & Prévôt, 2011](#)). Modelling time-series measurements for PM is thus challenging, and future research should aim to elucidate the governing mechanisms for the various factors determining the temporal variation in concentrations. It is particularly noteworthy that a change in the relative magnitude among the two stations for PM is happening at the beginning of May. Before this point, the station inside the park shows the highest concentrations for PM₁₀, identical concentrations for PM_{2.5} and slightly lower concentrations for PM₁, whereas after this point, the station outside the park shows the highest concentrations for all three PM fractions. This is accompanied by a change in the temporal pattern of the time series for PM. Up until the beginning of May, the temporal pattern for PM has been dominated by large scale variations which are typical of urban background. After the change at the beginning of May, the urban background concentration has been largely diminished, as seen by the low concentrations becoming close to zero. That this is a local scale phenomenon was confirmed by comparing the present measurements with nearby PM measurements from the Automatic Urban and Rural Network (AURN) ([Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2019](#)), where no sign of changes at the beginning of May was seen. This change becomes all the more surprising in that it does not correspond with the change in LAI as would have been expected. This indicates that the change is not caused by the greenup, as measured by the LAI, but could be related to other hedge properties such as density or “stickiness” of the leaves – properties that have not been measured in the present study.

It is also worth noting that the shift in concentration magnitude between the two stations does not happen for the gaseous pollutants measured (NO₂ and CO). This indicates that the hedge is influencing

Fig. 2. Time series of concentrations measured at the two stations (outside station = black, inside station = red, LAI = blue). Data have been low-pass filtered and subject to automatic quality control (see Section 2.5) to better visualise long-term changes.

gaseous and particulate matter pollutants differently.

3.2. Relative differences

The change happening at the beginning of May can be more clearly visualised by plotting the relative concentration ($C_{\text{inside}}/C_{\text{outside}}$) for all three pollutants and three fractions of PM as presented in Fig. 3. The black line is a piecewise function consisting of a constant, a straight line and a new constant fitted using the `fminsearch` function in Matlab. For this analysis, values of ($C_{\text{inside}}/C_{\text{outside}}$) > 3 have been removed as outliers since these will strongly influence the mean values although they only constitute 0%–4% of the data. It is clearly evident from Fig. 3 that the abrupt change for particles, as also seen in Fig. 2, is happening at the beginning of May from a relative concentration slightly above or below 1 to a relative concentration of approximately 0.55. This concentration reduction is substantially larger than the 15 %–25 % reported in Abhijith and Kumar (2019) for the same location. However, firstly the sensors in the present study are mounted closer to the hedge

and should thus measure a larger reduction, and secondly, the present study covers a much longer time period including periods of rain, night-time and weekends. On the other hand, the trend of the largest reduction for PM_{10} and the smallest reduction for PM_{10} is found both in the present and previous studies, e.g., in Abhijith and Kumar (2019) for hedges in Weerakkody, Dover, Mitchell, and Reiling (2017); and in Weerakkody, Dover, Mitchell, & Reiling (2018) for green walls and in Freer-Smith, Beckett, and Taylor (2005) for urban trees. All of these studies have been based on measurements, and future work should thus use models to elucidate the mechanisms behind this phenomenon.

The change in relative concentrations only occurred for particles and not for the two gaseous pollutants, indicating that the drop in relative concentrations caused by the hedge is dominated by the deposition of particles onto the leaves and branches of the hedge rather than the increased dilution as the wind flows over and through the hedge.

The different phases of the vegetation cycle, as measured by the LAI values, are indicated in the top of the figure. It is interesting to note that

Fig. 3. Time series of relative concentrations ($C_{inside}/C_{outside}$) for all five species. Colours represent the relative density of data points, with blue indicating low density and red indicating high density. The fitted constant values are marked with black lines. The growth phases are determined based on the LAI measurements.

the hedge reaches the maturity phase before the drop in relative concentrations. This indicates that LAI, as measured by the LP-80 ceptometer, is not a good measure of the change in relative concentrations. A potential explanation could be that the LAI is increasing as the hedge is greening up, but even after the hedge has turned green, the density of the hedge continues to increase, as observed by the experimenters on site. This mechanism could potentially be the cause of the drop in relative concentrations and future work should aim at measuring the hedge density by other methods than LAI. Another explanation could be related to a change in “stickiness” of the leaves of the hedge.

The raw data of Fig. 3 are shown with colours indicating the corresponding quartile of the pollutants for all five pollutants in SI Figure S6. It is evident for the three particulate matter pollutants as well as for CO, that the high and low concentrations are changing with time and are less influenced by the relative concentration. On the other hand, it is evident for NO₂ that the relative concentrations > 1 belongs to the first quartile of the distribution, whereas the higher absolute concentrations also show lower absolute concentrations.

Further insight can be gained by plotting the relative concentration of the five pollutants as a function of the absolute concentration of one of the stations, in this case, the station closest to the road, as plotted in Fig. 4 plus SI Figure S7-S8. The boxplots in Fig. 4 plus SI Figures S7-S8 are made for hourly averages, to reduce the uncertainty on the low concentrations. It is interesting to note that a systematic trend is seen towards lower relative concentrations for low absolute concentrations of particles as shown by the fitted exponential curves. The same pattern is not seen for gases. One possible explanation is that the low-cost sensors are not very sensitive to low concentrations as analysed in more detail in Section 3.4, which causes it to drop faster to zero compared to the high-end instruments.

The dependence of the relative concentrations on the absolute concentrations, as shown in Fig. 4 plus SI Figs. S7-S8, effectively precludes the analysis of the effect of rain, since there is a strong correlation between low concentrations of PM and a short time between the measurement and the last rainfall, as shown in SI Fig. S9.

Fig. 4. Boxplots of the relative concentrations as a function of the absolute concentration at the station outside the park for PM_{10} . The terms “before” and “after” refer to the breaks fitted in Fig. 3.

3.3. Effect of wind direction and efficacy of hedges

Further insight into the drop in relative concentrations can be gained by looking at the relative concentration between the two stations, before and after the concentration drop, as a function of wind direction as seen in Fig. 5. The absolute concentrations as a function of wind direction can be found in SI Fig. S10. The wind direction is seen to be a minor effect for most wind directions both before and after the drop in concentrations. This is surprising, since if the hedge was acting like a filter on the airflow, as is commonly believed, one should expect the relative concentration to be > 1 for wind directions in the interval $[0-180^\circ]$ and no influence of the road should be seen. One potential explanation is that the hedge may be acting as a solid barrier after the drop in relative concentrations during the maturity stage. This would mean that when the wind direction is in the interval $[0-180^\circ]$ a recirculation zone would be formed on the roadside of the hedge and push pollutants towards the sensor leading to higher concentrations. Similarly, when the wind direction is in the interval $[180-360^\circ]$ the sensor is downwind from the source and the wind would thus push pollutants towards the sensor leading to higher concentrations. Future work using computational fluid dynamics models should aim to explore the mechanisms of this effect.

The change in flow and concentrations of inert gaseous pollutants in the vicinity of a vegetation barrier as a function of leaf area density (LAD) was studied by Ghasemian, Amini, and Princevac (2017) using a computational fluid dynamics model. Unfortunately, their vegetation barrier is much larger than the hedge of the present study plus they only looked at one wind direction and wind speed. Moreover, their distance to the road is much larger than in the present study, which means substantial dilution has already happened before the interaction with the vegetation barrier. Their results are thus not directly comparable to ours. Nevertheless, they show that as the LAD of the vegetation barrier increases, the flow pattern is approaching that of a solid barrier, where a recirculation zone is dominating. Compared to their results, our LAD values are moving from $1.36 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ to $3.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ and is thus characterised as being closer to a solid barrier than to flat terrain.

3.4. Verification of low-cost sensors

The scatterplots of the low-cost sensor concentrations for PM and NO_2 versus the reference instruments are shown in Fig. 6. As seen, the robust direct proportionality fits show very high coefficients of determination. It can however also be seen that the fit is underestimating the reference concentrations for the low values. A better fit could

probably be obtained by fitting a nonlinear relationship, with a similar form as Fig. 4 plus SI Figures S7-S8, between the two datasets, but that would require more measurements of the low reference concentrations to determine the shape of the curve precisely. It is likely that this relates to the nonlinear effect seen for low concentrations in Section 3.2.

It was clear from Figs. 2 and 3 that there is a change in dilution-deposition pattern between the two sensors after the greenup. As seen from Fig. 2, the change happens simultaneously for both sensors. Since there is negligible difference in the residuals between the fitted curve and the measurements for the two co-location campaigns for the station outside the park, it is highly likely that the observed change is caused by the hedge between the two sensors and not by a change in sensor properties (such as drift).

4. Conclusions and Outlook

The present study measured five pollutants in front and behind a hedge, using low-cost sensors, over a long time period. The following conclusions have been reached: (1) The absolute PM concentrations in front and behind the hedge are dominated by meteorological, biological and societal variables as seen by e.g. half term and periods of rain. (2) The PM time series show a rapid drop after the greenup of the hedge leading to time-averaged reductions of up to 52%. That this drop is not seen for gasses indicates that the drop is caused by a change in the deposition. The lack of correlation with LAI is a topic for future investigations. Potential explanations could be the density of the hedge or the stickiness of the leaves. (3) The gaseous pollutants CO and NO_2 show smaller concentration reductions across the hedge. (4) Wind direction is shown to be of minor importance.

These findings are relevant for urban planners in that it is, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the first quantification of the effects of the vegetation cycle on the interplay between deciduous hedges and traffic-generated air pollution. This provides strength to the hypothesis that coniferous hedges are preferable to deciduous hedges since the former will show large air pollution mitigation effects irrespective of the stages of the vegetation cycle, although this remains to be shown.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first time the drop in particle concentrations as a function of the vegetation cycle has been shown. To fortify the understanding of this phenomenon, replication studies should be carried out on other hedges and over longer time periods (e.g. multi-year studies) to determine if this is a repeating phenomenon. These should preferably try to find the controlling variables e.g. hedge density or leaf stickiness. Likewise, other street geometries could be measured to explore the general applicability of the

Fig. 5. Boxplot of the relative concentrations as a function of wind direction before and after (red = relative concentrations before jump, green = relative concentrations after jump) the jump in concentrations for all five species. The terms “before” and “after” refer to the breaks fitted in Fig. 3.

present results.

This study measured concentrations at one height and one distance to the hedge. One remaining question is where the largest concentration reductions are observed with respect to height and distance from the hedge. By using a larger number of sensors, it would be possible to measure the full two-dimensional concentration field on both sides of the hedge.

The present results are based on measurements using low-cost sensors and no calibration are applied to the obtained dataset. The results should thus be interpreted as indicative measurements and future studies with calibrated or high-end instruments would contribute to reduced uncertainties on the results obtained.

Author contribution

PK designed and conceptualised the study plus obtained funding for the study and TBO implemented the plan and analysed the data. Both authors contributed equally to the writing up of the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Fig. 6. Scatterplot of low-cost sensor concentration versus reference instrument concentration (black). The red lines are direct proportionality fits fitted through robust regression, and R^2 is the coefficient of determination.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2019.101919>.

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